

Frontline Leadership in Nursing

A systematic appraisal of nurses' perceptions and experiences of frontline leadership and its implications for team dynamics in a Magnet-recognized hospital

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Abstract

Nursing leadership influences staff experience, team functioning, and the quality and safety of care delivered across healthcare settings. This study was developed to examine how nurses perceive and experience frontline leadership in a Magnet-recognized hospital and to explore the implications of those perceptions for team dynamics, staff retention, and quality of care. The project used a systematic appraisal approach based on review of relevant published research, with secondary data gathered and organized to identify recurring themes across the literature. The analysis was conducted thematically and presented narratively. The findings indicate that frontline nurse leaders require strong organizational, communication, and management capabilities in addition to visible leadership behaviors that support empowerment, trust, and staff engagement. Across the reviewed literature, nurses placed particular value on leadership that was present, accessible, supportive, and enabling, with these factors shaping team climate and influencing perceptions of effectiveness. The appraisal supports the view that frontline leadership is not only an administrative function but also a practical determinant of team coherence and care quality within high-performing nursing environments.

Keywords: nursing leadership; frontline leadership; Magnet-recognized hospitals; nurse perceptions; team dynamics; work environment

Note on terminology: Where the original manuscript used the phrase "Magnet accredited hospital," this public edition standardizes that phrasing to "Magnet-recognized hospital" to align with common ANCC terminology.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

Introduction

Magnet status is an award that is normally presented to hospitals by American Nurses' Credentialing Centre (ANCC) which is an affiliate of the American Nurses Association. Both are bodies that care for the nurses and take them into account. Hospitals that get to receive this form of status are those that have achieved a set of criteria that are designed to measure the strength and quality of their nursing services (Friese et al, 2015). A magnet hospital is defined by its ability to deliver excellent patient outcomes, it is where the nurses have a very high level of job satisfaction and is also characterized by low staff nurse turnover rate and appropriate grievance resolution. These facilities also have a lot of nurse involvement in data collection and decision making when it comes to patient care delivery plans. Basically, the leaders of these facilities have an attitude of involving the nurses in most of the evidence based practice and at the same time appreciate the nurses for the work that they are doing (Friese et al, 2015).

Over the last 30 years Magnet has been refined and extended beyond hospitals to include all healthcare organizations. In 2000, it went worldwide to become the only international accreditation scheme for nursing excellence. Today there are two programmes: the Magnet Recognition Program itself and the Pathway to Excellence, an intermediary programme for organizations at an early stage of their journey to Magnet recognition (ANCC, 2017a).

In the US, there are around 600 Magnet hospitals (8% of all US hospitals); they include most of the country's leading medical centres. Seven Magnet hospitals are outside of the US: three in Australia, two in Saudi Arabia, one in Canada and one in Lebanon. Interest is growing in Europe, with hospitals in Belgium, Germany, Spain and the UK seeking recognition (ANCC, 2017a).

The process is lengthy but can be a revealing self-assessment exercise, providing valuable feedback and creating opportunities for improvement. As achieving Magnet status requires a commitment over several years, it offers a long-term framework for quality improvement and for engaging and empowering staff at all levels.

There are many benefits to pursuing Magnet status, even before accreditation is granted. Studies suggest improvements in nurse turnover, staff and patient satisfaction, and clinical outcomes. Other quantifiable staff benefits include improved nurse education, less burnout and fewer occupational injuries (ANCC, 2017b).

Studies have also shown improved patient outcomes including lower mortality rates, fewer medication errors, less post-surgical treatment for general surgery and orthopaedics, and fewer falls and pressure ulcers (ANCC, 2017b)

Magnet recognition and designation is the apex of nursing achievement and organizational nursing success (Wolf et al., 2008). Achieving Magnet designation means that an organization has created an infrastructure of interdisciplinary care that promotes the highest quality care and successfully integrates best practice, and produces exceptional patient care outcomes, while promoting collaboration and shared-decision making (Armstrong & Laschinger, 2006). Transformational leaders progressively recognize that Magnet designation displays an organization's ability to motivate healthcare workers towards a shared vision and intensify their commitment to the organization. The biggest advantages to cultivating a Magnet environment is it increases job satisfaction, increases morale and increases job performance by creating a meaningful and valued work environment as per (McGuire & Kennerly 2006).

The American Nurses Credentialing Center's (ANCC) Magnet recognition program is the marker of distinction for hospitals when discussing excellence in care. Accompanying this designation is the feeling of an entitlement of superiority in hospital patient care outcomes and measurements as this designation is considered the pinnacle of all designations in healthcare throughout the United States (McGuire & Kennerly 2006). Since Magnet's inception in the 1980's, ANCC has promoted and encouraged this designation to be achieved by hospitals. Initially, Magnet was linked to recruiting and retaining nurses in order to provide superb care (Aiken, Buchan, Ball, & Rafferty, 2009).

In the early 1990's, ANCC identified Magnet hospitals as those organizations that promoted nursing excellence through work environments which promoted improved outcomes, increased job satisfaction, and reduced turnover (McGuire & Kennerly 2006). Being designated as a Magnet organization provides hospitals with a robust nursing culture as hospitals strive to be the best. In 2010, approximately 7% of hospitals had Magnet status (McGuire & Kennerly 2006). Finally, McGuire & Kennerly (2006) reported that a substantial variation in perceptions about professional nursing governance

Nurse administrators must have comprehensive knowledge of their organization to create opportunities for change and enhance programs and processes that create a culture of shared governance and commitment (Sokol, 2004). Effective leadership and transformational leaders are aware that the amount of time nurse they spend with front-line nurses impacts their ability to empower and engage staff. Upenieks (2003) reported that visibility and accessibility were rated among the highest traits of effective leaders

Problem statement

Quality care and patient safety should be of the highest priority for all healthcare providers, healthcare organizations, and healthcare consumers. When hiring new nurses, hospitals should seek candidates who are experienced because quality and safety are closely linked to experience and education levels (Aiken et al., 2003). Additionally, mortality rates and patient outcomes are closely linked to experience (Curtin, 2003).

Concurrently, nurses are seeking employment at organizations that promote the professional nurse and exemplify best practice in nursing care. The quest for the finest nursing staff, highest quality care, and optimal levels of patient safety is uniquely aligned with the quest for Magnet Recognition.

The total organizational cost to replace a registered nurse begins at \$42,000 for a medical/surgical nurse and \$64,000 for an intensive care unit nurse (Force, 2005). Upenieks (2003) study of retention and recruitment strategies suggested that a turnover rate reduction from 20% to 9 % would amount to saving nearly a million dollars annually for one magnet hospital. As per (Aiken et al., 2003) the concept of magnetism can be applied in any health care setting where nurses practice, in order to identify barriers and enhancing factors that influence the hospital work environment. In this study, the finding that the mean value of the nurses' perceptions of the importance of all forces of magnetism was more than any other factor because it is the basis for this study. It is the only way to get to understand for the way the nurses get to understand the feeling and the responsibility that comes with the roles.

Positive leadership and Visibility

Many leadership articles discussed the positive impact of visibility and accessibility on retention and staff satisfaction. Upenieks (2003) reported that visibility and accessibility were rated among the highest traits of effective leaders. Another study by (Duffield et al, 2011) of nearly 2500 nurses reported critical leadership skills included visibility, staff recognition and staff consultation Patrick et al (2011) reported that the reduction and restructuring of middle management nursing in Canada had resulted in reduced visibility, limited access, nursing dissatisfaction, decreased levels of empowerment and unsatisfactory work environments.

There are numerous publications recognizing leadership style as a key element for quality of healthcare. Effective leadership is among the most critical components that lead an organization to effective and successful outcomes. Significant positive associations between effective styles of leadership and high levels of patient satisfaction and reduction of adverse effects have been reported.

Effective leadership has an indirect impact on reducing mortality rates, by inspiring, retaining and supporting experienced staff. Although there are many published studies that indicate the importance of leadership, few of these studies have attempted to correlate a certain leadership style with patient outcomes and healthcare quality indicators.

More recent theories of leadership – combining aspects of both personal trait and situational theories – recognize that effective leadership depends on the personality of the leader, the situation at hand and the qualities of the followers (Grossman & Valiga, 2012).

Leadership is not a haphazard occurrence, rather involves vision, communicating that vision to others, planning to make it a reality and serving as a symbol and source of energy for the team (Grossman & Valiga, 2012). It is therefore an extension of the notion of 'bringing order to chaos', noted above as being intrinsic to nursing leadership.

Positive quality care outcomes support patient care excellence throughout the entire organization and are reflective of higher levels of nurse satisfaction. Nurse satisfaction scores strongly influences the Magnet designation process. Overall, healthy work environments improved collaboration, communication, quality outcomes, and the satisfaction levels of patients and nurses. These studies were essential to planning the intervention because they all highlight the relationship between organizational leadership characteristics, professional practice and empowerment, nurse satisfaction and the nurse work environment.

Aims and Objectives

This study aims to explore nurses' perceptions and experiences of frontline leadership in Magnet hospital and its implication on team dynamics in order to identify areas of improvement in nurses' leadership to enhance quality of practice. To change and to improve current practice.

General research question

Which dominant leadership style are frontline managers practicing in Magnet-recognized facilities?

Specific research questions

What is the impact of this leadership style on work environment in Magnet hospitals?

How does frontline leadership affect team dynamics?

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

There is always a desire for positive outcome by all facilities. This is always aimed at making a very huge impact and transformation in the healthcare environment. The goals of the hospital leadership are to attain very high levels of worker satisfaction, patients also need to be satisfied by the services that they receive and at the same time, there is the aspect of retention of employees and the attainment of high quality of care (Callicutt, 2015). These outcomes are not achieved by sitting back and having a period of rest. They always come as a result of having the right structure and the right organizational staff and goals that are aimed at propelling the organization in a forward direction (Callicutt, 2015). According to the American Nurses Credentialing Center (ANCC), magnet recognition refers to meeting certain criteria by which a hospital is able to withstand nursing shortages, and

attract and retain nurses. The criteria include 5 magnet model components and 14 forces of: 1) Transformational Leadership (encompasses 2 Forces: Quality of Nursing Leadership, Management Style); 2) Structural Empowerment (encompasses 5 Forces: Organizational Structure, Personnel Policies and Programs, Community and the Healthcare Organization, Image of Nursing, Professional Development); 3) Exemplary Professional Practice (encompasses 5 Forces: Professional Models of Care, Consultation and Resources, Autonomy, Nurses as Teachers, Interdisciplinary Relationships); 4) New Knowledge, Innovations and Improvements (encompasses 1 Force: Quality Improvement); 5) Empirical Outcome (encompasses 1 Force: Quality of Care).

Another study that was done by (Kutney-Leen et al, 2015) which aimed to identify the satisfaction levels of nurses with positive environment initiatives and positive management strategies.

In total, 235 and 259 nurses participated in the study before and after the application of the initiatives and strategies, respectively. Strategies adopted from the magnet model to create positive work environments and management styles were executed according to the forces of magnetism. Data related to satisfaction were collected twice, once before and once after the strategies to create positive working environments were implemented.

The rates of working environment satisfaction in the nurses' department were 57.07% in 2011 and 69.01% in 2013. The rate of satisfaction with governance differed significantly between 2011 and 2013, especially in terms of the merit system, equity and equality, information flow between the administration and the employees, and the influence of the nursing managers on institutional decision making. (Kutney-Leen et al, 2015). This study showed (Kutney-Leen et al, 2015) that 24 months after the implementation of these strategies, nurse satisfaction with their work environment and management style increased significantly.

Callicutt (2015) had conducted a study that aims to identify recent research related to nursing leadership and management effects on work environment using the 14 forces of magnetism. Throughout reviewing historical perspective from the original 1983 American Academy of Nursing study through to the 2002 McClure and Hinshaw update to 2009 publications. This study had found correlations among positive workplace management initiatives, style of transformational leadership and participative management; patient-to-nurse ratios; education levels of nurses; quality of patient care, patient satisfaction, employee health and well-being programmes; nurse satisfaction and retention of nurses; healthy workplace environments and healthy patients and personnel.

Aiken et al (2008) also had conducted a study to evaluate the impact of interventions designed to improve the nursing work environment on patient and nurse outcomes. This quasi-experimental study involved 16 unit managers, 1,137 patients, and 296 observations from registered nurses over time. As a result, study nurses reported higher perceptions of

their work and work environment. Demographic nurse, unit, and hospital characteristics also had an impact on the work environment and outcomes. Findings in this study highlight the importance of understanding factors in the work environment that influence patient and nurse outcomes.

(Aiken et al., 2008) had conducted a pre-post analysis in England, within the first hospital to achieve Magnet status outside of the United States. Significant changes in features of the work environment and outcomes after Magnet recognition were found, including increased nurse autonomy and administrative support. The results from this case study suggest that changes in the work environment resulted from the requirements for successful Magnet recognition.

Another study was done by (Kutney-Lee et al., 2015) concluded that, through the Magnet process, hospitals undergo a transformation that includes significant improvements in the quality of the nurse work environment. Overall, hospitals that obtain Magnet recognition demonstrate significant improvements in patient and nurse job outcomes over time that exceed those of their non-Magnet peers. As one of the first longitudinal studies of Magnet hospitals, our findings provide early evidence for a potential causal link between the improvement of nurse work environments and patient outcomes.

The literature has identified the significance of leadership styles and practices on patient outcomes, health care workforce and organizational culture. Setting effective leadership as a priority in health care units is expected to enhance a variety of measurable indicators, even in fragmented health systems (Gibson et al., 2004).

According to (Lundmark, 2008.) more and more regional and national health systems tend to undergo structural changes and redesign their functions and priorities in order to face modern societal, economic, and health challenges and needs. A study that was done by (Lundmark, 2008.) had revealed that medical leadership in decision-making is a key component in order to develop a successful and qualitative priority setting process in health care. Multilevel Poisson regression analyses indicated that the benefits of safety organizing on reported medication errors were amplified when paired with high levels of trust in manager or the use of care pathways.

Safety organizing plays a key role in improving patient safety on hospital nursing units especially when bundled with other organizational components of a safety supportive system. Most importantly, engagement of non-medical clinical leaders, such as nursing leadership, is considered to ensure the legitimacy and validity of priority setting. As shown in the present study, the leadership styles that proved to be more effective and promoted positive outcomes were those that conceptualize management as a collaborative, multifaceted, and dynamic process (e.g., transformational, employee-oriented leadership).

To be more effective leaders and full partners, nurses need to possess two critical sets of competencies: a common set that can serve as the foundation for any leadership opportunity and a more specific set tailored to a particular context, time, and place. The former set includes, among others, knowledge of the care delivery system, how to work in teams, how to collaborate effectively within and across disciplines, the basic tenets of ethical care, how to be an effective patient advocate, theories of innovation, and the foundations for quality and safety improvement.

These competencies also are recommended by the American Association of Colleges of Nursing as essential for baccalaureate programs (AACN, 2008). Leadership competencies recommended by the National League for Nursing and National League for Nursing Accrediting Commission are being revised to reflect similar principles. More specific competencies might include learning how to be a full partner in a health team in which members from various professions hold each other accountable for improving quality and decreasing preventable adverse events and medication errors. Additionally, nurses who are interested in pursuing entrepreneurial and business development opportunities need competencies in such areas as economics and market forces, regulatory frameworks, and financing policy.

Background

Nurse managers' leadership roles may be viewed as challenging given the complex needs of patients and staff nurses' involvement in both clinical and organizational decision-making processes in interdisciplinary care settings. A qualitative phenomenological study was conducted by (Lundmark, 2008.), where Individual semi-structured interviews were conducted with 8 medical or surgical nurse managers in a 600-bed Belgian university hospital between December 2013 and June 2014. This hospital was undergoing conversion from a classical hierarchical, departmental structure to a flat, interdisciplinary model.

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Leadership styles play an integral role in enhancing quality measures in health care and nursing. Impact on health-related outcomes differs according to the different leadership styles, while they may broaden or close the existing gap in health care. Addressing the leadership gap in health care in an evolving and challenging environment constitutes the

current and future goal of all societies. Health care organizations need to ensure technical and professional expertise, build capacity, and organizational culture, and balance leadership priorities and existing skills in order to improve quality indicators in health care and move a step forward. Interpretation of the current review's outcomes and translation of the main messages into implementation practices in health care and nursing settings is strongly suggested.

Results revealed that nurse managers were found to be familiar with the structural empowerment of clinical nurses in the hospital and to hold positive attitudes toward it. They confirmed the positive impact of empowerment on their staff nurses, as evidenced by increased responsibility, autonomy, critical reflection and enhanced communication skills that in turn improved the quality and safety of patient care. Structural empowerment was being supported by several change initiatives at both the unit and hospital levels. Nurse managers' experiences with these initiatives were mixed, however, because of the changing demands with regard to their manager role and leadership style. In addition, pressure was being experienced by both staff nurses and nurse managers as a result of direct patient care priorities, tightly scheduled projects and miscommunication (Lundmark, 2008.).

This study had concluded (Gibson et al., 2004) that nurse managers reported that structural empowerment was having a favorable impact on staff nurses' professional attitudes and the safety and quality of care in their units. However, they also reported that the empowerment process had led to changes in the managers' roles as well as daily practice dilemmas related to the leadership styles needed. Clear organizational goals and dedicated support for both clinical nurses and nursing unit managers are imperative to maintaining an empowering practice environment which can ensure the best care and healthy, engaged staff.

Empowerment according to other professions

Page and Czuba (1999) identified empowerment in terms of a social process in which individuals gain control over their personal lives by challenging assumptions that involve power, assistance, achievement, and success. They believed that there is really no formula towards being empowered in real sense but it involves being able to take the world and the challenges that it brings along with a positive attitude and also being able to find ways around them (Page & Czuba, 1999). It is seen that empowerment comes with the delegation of duty as well as autonomy in most instances. This is basically an explanation that tries to bring out the point that for one to be defined as being empowered then he/she should be showing the characteristics of being able to make choices for himself and herself and these choices have to be those that lead to positive impacts.

Empowerment in Nursing

As other disciplines and professions provide insight as to what is empowerment, the profession of nursing links important traits to this concept. Even though empowerment has been defined by many individuals and disciplines, the concept resonates with many meanings. In nursing, many nurse scientists have defined empowerment and how this concept correlates with many outcomes. According to management, Page & Czuba (1999) state that employees are engaged at all organizational levels when participating in decisions for the organization. In essence, the definition of empowerment for nurses is accredited to the business world.

Empowerment contributes to positive organizational outcomes as nurses' address workplace problems and augment decision-making skills while feeling in control. Empowerment allows the employee to be stretched to reach their full potential (Page & Czuba, 1999) performed a cross-sectional correlational study with randomized sample of 322 staff nurses in acute care hospitals in Ontario. These authors tested Kanter's organizational empowerment theory and Maslach and Leiter's work engagement model. Nurses rated total empowerment as being moderate ($M = 18.43$; $SD = 3.41$). Nurses rated access to opportunity as being the greatest ($M = 3.98$; $SD = 0.81$) and formal power as being the least empowering factor ($M = 2.49$; $SD = 0.85$). Nurses reported high levels of burnout ($M = 3.17$; $SD = 1.50$).

Even though power is often correlated with empowerment, the two must not be confused. Page & Czuba (1999) emphasizes that power essentially is the ability to impose one's will upon others as power is associated with control, influence, or domination and connected to legal and/or coercive behaviors. When nurses lack power in the work environment, they often become dissatisfied with their jobs and become ineffective in productivity (Page & Czuba, 1999). Being ineffective or dissatisfied may lead to burnout. Empowerment is important to have in the work environment because it enables employees to act. When nurses are empowered, they develop independent health-promoting behaviors because they are able to think, problem solve, and make autonomous choices (Page & Czuba, 1999). When employees are provided this trust, satisfaction and dedication will be exhibited by the employee. Thus, the question imposed becomes centered on what type of empowerment exists in nursing.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

Purpose

The main reason for carrying out this study is to find out what the nurses really think of the leadership positions in the Magnet hospitals. This is aimed at evaluating their thoughts and interpretation of the roles that are played by various leaders and the things they feel should have been done differently to help in keeping these organizations at the magnet

state. It involves the assessment of their roles in making sure there is retention of nurses as well as improvement of quality of care so as to maintain the high standards of the already awarded institutions that they have already been given the credentials.

Design

This research utilized a correlational, cross-sectional design to evaluate the relationship between structural empowerment and job satisfaction, intent to stay in the work setting, perceptions about quality of care, and perception about medication errors respectively in Magnet. Also, the practice environment was evaluated to see if Magnet hospitals are superior in components that cater to this designation. Nursing quality data, quality of care and medication errors, were also collected. A cross-sectional design allowed data to be collected only once during a single period.

A survey done through all the papers that were done by some of the nurses were equally used in the formulation of this paper. They were equally important as they were sources of first-hand information that aided in the development of much more insight to this paper. These indeed served as the very best and typically accurate information sources. They were chosen on the basis of the best known health issues writer nurses.

There will also be the use of secondary data that will help in the formulation of what the research that have been carried out before have on this topic. This information will be obtained in a very sequential and orderly manner in order to be able to come up with secondary data that is equally useful in this study.

Methods

The researcher met with the nursing research councils of the two major organizations and corresponded via electronically and telephonic to the one smaller rural facility. The meetings were conducted to obtain permission to conduct the research at their respective institutions or organizations. Nurse participants were recruited through the healthcare system's electronic mail system. An email was sent to all nurses working for the specific market of the organizations chosen. The email contained an electronic letter explaining the purpose and importance of the study. A survey link was embedded within the email which directed them to an independent website for data collection. Access to the link was available through any computer that had internet access. The survey was available for approximately four weeks for data collection. To assure anonymity, no identification codes were linked to any completed electronic surveys.

After analyzing the research questions and study hypotheses, it was determined that five hypotheses required the largest sample size for adequate statistical power to detect an association between empowerment subscales and the measure being evaluated. A medium effect size of Cohen's $f^2 = 0.25$ between structural empowerment level and the other measures was detected with a 2-way logistic regression with at least 80% power

when the sample size was 209 nurses, assuming a two-tailed type I error = 0.00625 (i.e., 0.05/8 for the eight types of job satisfaction) and adjusting for gender, race/ethnicity, age, years in nursing, years in current nursing position, years in nursing, education level, length of shift, professional job role, typical shift worked, and average hours worked per week.

Evidence search

This section of this study dealt with the method of data analysis that was to be used in the development of the results that were in the end going to lead to a discussion and the final conclusion of the study. This was going to be based on scientific methods that were much more relevant and easier to understand with a lot of it based on the facts that were associated with the collection and synthesis of data obtained. This systematic review was carried out according to the recommendations of PRISMA (Shamseer, 2015). The methods were to outline the search criteria used and would identify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the studies selected.

The electronic databases were used to search for relevant articles for this review. This was because the named data bases were considered as some of the best and most informative sources of information on physiotherapy (Methley , 2014). They provided for very high quality and top notch studies that were very informative and well-designed papers for this topic. To define the search terms for this review, Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes and Study type (PICOS) was used as it stands as one of the best and most effective tools in the collection of data that was related to this field of study.

It has been shown to be effective in highlighting areas of interest and has been shown to provide relevant and valid articles when a systematic review is conducted (Methley , 2014). PICOS is also a more suitable approach to searching for studies in comparison to the PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison and Outcomes) approach when searching for qualitative research (Ridley, 2012). This indeed makes it very effective as a way of being able to gather all the data that is needed in the study and in the making of concrete data for a conclusion to be drawn in the end.

A manual hand search of the returned studies to examine if previous fallers comprised the sample or not will take place. Studies that did include previous fallers will be included and those that do not will be excluded from tis review. This is an effective approach to ensuring of the most accurate returns within systematic reviews (Armstrong, 2005). An initial screening of the abstract and title of the returned studies would be conducted. If these papers had no mention of any of the inclusion criteria, the full text would be obtained and screened for eligibility criteria to see if these could be included in this review.

As already illustrated, the primary source of data was mainly the use of the databases. This was because it is already very evident that there are a lot of advantages that come along with the fact that that site is one that is very comprehensive in this topic. It was also found to be rich in all the information in this area of study as most of the authors in this particular field have come up with a lot of information that is connected to the to the study and the use of various ways of temperature determination as a form of treatment for these kind of children.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were formed alongside the selected search terms to obtain the most relevant studies for this review. The inclusion and exclusion criteria were operationalized at two different points depending on the nature of the criteria. The first being when, criteria such as; date of publication, being full text accessible and published in English could be operationalized when in the search stage through using search operators and search filters. The second being, when criteria such as; the definition of ‘children’, grey literature or being commentaries or review papers – can only be defined at the point of the initial manual paper search from the returned results. This approach is in line with the recommendations advised regarding the process of conducting a review (Armstrong, 2005)

Inclusion criteria

Studies that are primary research

Studies published between 2008 – 2018 to select the most up to date evidence is returned – falls prevention programmes have developed considerably during this timeframe (Charlton et al., 2018). A focused time parameter will provide specificity of returns (Page, 2008).

Studies published in English

Studies in which participants had suffered at least one fall

Studies where all participants were aged 5 or below and considered ‘children’.

Studies that are full text accessible

Exclusion criteria

Not meeting the inclusion criteria

Dissertations, grey literature or doctoral theses

Quantitative or mixed methods research papers

Opinion papers, review papers or commentaries

In order to effectively undertake a systematic literature review, it is dependent upon two key factors; if sufficient studies are present within the body of literature (Kitchenham, 2004). The other is, in the case of an over-abundance of studies meeting search criteria, the

rapid yet accurate sifting of returned papers (Kitchenham, 2004). Prior to implementing a database search, it is good practice for a priori protocol to be developed to manually identify and narrow down studies to select only the most relevant from many returned studies (Booth, Sutton & Papaioannou, 2016).

Data Extraction, Synthesis and Analysis

Data has been drawn into a table whereby each study has been assessed for the key findings, the scientific rigor as well as the approach. This method is used commonly for data extraction and synthesis which therefore allows for comparisons to be made and contextualized between each study in relation to key findings, similarities and differences (Dixon-Woods et al., 2007). This table includes the reference of each study, the title, number of participants, method of data collection, findings, method of analysis and the strengths and weaknesses.

To be able to successfully synthesize the data, the method for doing this for qualitative studies has been highlighted by the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) (NHS – Public health resource unit, 2006). This method of assessment criteria allows for the rigor of qualitative studies to be objectively considered. It is accepted that the experiences, views and preconceptions of the researcher may have an influence on the way the studies are interpreted (Parahoo, 2014). However, as there are financial restrictions and time constraints for postgraduate students, this can be unavoidable (Peters, 2012). This will be considered within the discussion of the limitations of the review.

The key findings will be analyzed from the included studies which will aim to loosely employ the framework for thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke's, 2006). This framework consists of six stages of analysis, whereby the data is read-through and organized into codes and themes which reflect the content. This is a way to provide for a robust means of analyzing data and enables being able to identify key themes and patterns across the different studies. This method of approach allows for the aims and objectives of the current review to be met in a transparent and robust manner.

Demographic information

The demographic information form was developed for this study to obtain characteristics about the nurse participants. The individual information collected included the participant's place of employment, gender, race, age, number of years in nursing, number of years in current nursing role, number of years on the nursing unit, number of hours worked in a typical week, length of shift worked, shift of work, work status, primary unit of employment, job role, and education. Also, the individual was asked if their organization was on the pathway for excellence for Magnet. These measures were selected from a review of the literature on structural empowerment and Magnet organizations

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction was measured by the JSS. This questionnaire consists of 36 items designed to measure job satisfaction, and this tool uses a six point Likert scale to evaluate responses. This instrument measures several scales which include pay, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards (performance based upon rewards), operating procedures (required rules and procedures), coworkers, nature of work, and communication. Cronbach alpha reliabilities are as follow: pay (0.75), promotion (0.73), supervision (0.82), fringe benefits (0.73), contingent rewards (0.76), operating procedures (0.62), coworkers (0.60), nature of work (0.78), and communication (0.71). Total Cronbach alpha reliability is 0.91 for all facets of this instrument (Summers, 2014). The JSS was examined from the 2004 National Database of Nursing Quality Indictors ® which examined job satisfaction among direct care nurses (Upenieks, 2003).

Quality of Care

Quality of care was measured by asking three questions. One item, which has been used to evaluate perceived quality of care, has been used repetitively in multiple studies (Aiken & Poghosyam, 2009). Two other questions will be asked in addition to evaluate quality of care (Aiken et al, 2008; Ridley et al., 2009). There have been no studies that report reliability or validity. Multiple studies have examined nursing and quality of care (Aiken & Poghosyan, 2009).

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS 19.0 software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL). Descriptive statistics were performed to assess for outliers. Assumptions of analyses were checked including normality, linearity, and homoscedasticity where appropriate. The data were examined to determine if they were theoretically out of range. A two sided p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

CHAPTER FOUR: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Job satisfaction

Results of the Job Satisfaction Scale (JSS) provided information concerning the state of how nurses feel about their work environment. Findings regarding JSS scores, total and subscales, were mixed. Nurses in both types of organizations agreed that the nature of work was the highest subscale as this subscale addressed job tasks. Nurses from both types of organizations differed in the least favorable subscale as Magnet nurses reported pay, focusing on pay and remuneration, to be the least favorable and non-Magnet nurses reported promotions, focusing on promotion opportunities, to be the least favorable. When comparing Magnet and non-Magnet organizations in this study, nurses did perceive job satisfaction as being slightly satisfying (M = 146.01; SD = 27.18). Magnet nurses had an

average total score of 145.89 (SD = 26.98) and non-Magnet nurses had an average score of 146.36 (SD = 27.79).

There was no statistical difference when comparing both types of organizations when looking at total job satisfaction scores ($p = 0.810$). The American Nurses Credentialing Center claims that one of the benefits of Magnet designation includes attracting and retaining top talent, improving patient care, safety, and satisfaction, and fostering a collaborative culture. Retaining talent involves having satisfied employees. Results from this study show that Magnet and non-Magnet organizations are similar in job satisfaction scores according to the JSS ($p = 0.810$). The subscales from this instrument were similar in both types of organizations with no statistical significance in any subscale.

Perceptions about Medication Errors and Quality of Care

When comparing Magnet and non-Magnet organizations in this study, nurses did perceive quality outcomes similarly. Both types of organizations reported the highest about never having a medication error within the last year. Magnet nurses were at 52.4% reporting whereas non-Magnet nurses were at 47.0% reporting. Magnet nurses reported that they rarely had a medication error within the last year (39.8%) whereas non-Magnet nurses reported 43.5%. Perceived quality of care provided some interesting results. When assessing quality of care between both types of organizations, Magnet nurses reported quality of care delivered on the last shift as excellent (60.6%), quality of care delivered during the shift as excellent (63.8%), quality of care improved over the last year (35.4%) and confident to very confident that patients could take care of themselves at discharge (80.4%).

Non-Magnet nurses reported quality of care delivered on the last shift as excellent (56.5%), quality of care delivered during the shift as excellent (59.2%), quality of care improved over the last year (37.1%) and confident to very confident that patients could take care of themselves at discharge (68.9%). Concerning in the results is the fact that nurses in both types of organizations reported that quality of care had declined (15.9%). As healthcare organizations struggle to cut costs, nurse administrators will need to address this concern as quality of care will have to be continually improved for reimbursements to occur. Overall, results from this study did indicate that quality of care was perceived to be better in Magnet organizations as percentages were higher in all categories except for quality of care over the last year.

Implications

The results of this study provide a valuable description about whether or not a difference exists between Magnet and non-Magnet organizations. Outcomes assessed included structural empowerment, job satisfaction, anticipated turnover, and quality of care measures. These measurements compared the two different types of organizations to see

whether or not a difference truly existed and where opportunities for improvement are needed. This information may assist other healthcare organizations in deciding about whether or not Magnet designation needs to be achieved or not. This research does provide guidance as to how nurses feel about their work environment. More research is needed to compare Magnet and non-Magnet organizations where similar institution can be compared

Study Limitations

The limitations associated with this research study must be considered with any interpretations. This study involved 21 healthcare organizations. Two corporate hospital organizations comprised 20 of the 21 hospitals participating with both corporations having both types of organizations, Magnet and non-Magnet facilities. Some non-Magnet hospitals were on the pathway of excellence for Magnet designation. Another limitation is that the environment from the healthcare organization may be different. Magnet organizations tended to reside in urban environments whereas non-Magnet organizations tended to reside in rural environments.

The population served, as well as the size of the facility, by these different facilities varied which could certainly influence the perceptions of nurses regarding work environment and quality of care. Another limitation involved the length of the survey and completion rates. Questions at the end of the survey tended to be left blank as the survey was comprised of four instruments and a demographic section. Finally, an electronic survey was used for this survey and a malfunction was detected in the first few days of survey distribution which may have prevented some nurses from completing the survey.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION

Conclusion

Leadership from nurses is needed at every level and across all settings. Although collaboration is generally a commendable goal, there are many times when nurses, for the sake of delivering exceptional patient and family care, must step into an advocate role with a singular voice. At the same time, effective leadership also requires recognition of situations in which it is more important to mediate, collaborate, or follow others who are acting in leadership roles. Nurses must understand that their leadership is as important to providing quality care as is their technical ability to deliver care at the bedside in a safe and effective manner. They must lead in improving work processes on the frontlines; creating new integrated practice models; working with others, from organizational policy makers to state legislators, to craft practice policy and legislation that allows nurses to work to their fullest capacity; leading curriculum changes to prepare the nursing workforce to meet community and patient needs; translating and applying research findings into practice and developing functional models of care; and serving on

institutional and policy-making boards where critical decisions affecting patients are made.

Nurse leaders at every level and position must develop organizational and management skills, whether they are managing human, fiscal, policy, time, material or other resources. Similarly, nursing administrators at every level must hone strong leadership skills to be effective administrators. Exerting good management skills is part of being a good leader – and leadership skills are necessary for good management. It is also important to have it in mind that the nurses also have a lot of preference to areas where they are being empowered. This makes them feel like they are part of the leadership that is in place at all times. It also makes them feel like they are growing and are having advancement in their careers as well. Thus makes them always feel more alive and in position.

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